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Post-Industrial Korea: Role Of State in Fostering Innovation, CCEI Initiative of Park Geun-Hye

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Abstract

South Korea's¹ rapid transformation from a war-torn agrarian economy to an advanced industrial power has been primarily attributed to the strong role played by the developmental state, where the state utilises various tools and policies to foster domestic industry development and economic transformation. However, while the manufacturing sector was once the primary growth driver, the current economy is witnessing a shift towards the service industry, marking South Korea's gradual transition into a post-industrial society. The paper tends to look at how the state's role has been transforming and how it has turned into a facilitator for growth and development. The paper has one central question: How has the role of the state evolved as the economy transitioned into a post-industrial economy, particularly in relation to innovation and entrepreneurship? The paper concludes that the state has helped to facilitate a sustainable and productive ecosystem for innovation by leveraging its high-skilled and educated workforce and its highly advanced infrastructure.

Keywords: Post-Industrial Society; Creative Economy; Innovation; Triple-Helix Model; State-Led Innovation.

1. Introduction

Park Geun Hye's administration's intention was to lead the "second miracle on the Han river" by fostering "creative start-ups and entrepreneurs" and with the state acting as a facilitator. These efforts of Park Geun Hye were also carried on by the next administration of Moon Jae-in. In 2017, the Moon administration elevated the support for SMEs to the ministerial level by establishing the Ministry of SMEs and Start-ups. Since the financial crisis, the chaebols and the new start-ups were instrumental in catapulting the economy (Jung, 2022). Whilst the chaebols increasingly took the shape of global firms, the new start-ups reflected a new chapter of the country's economy. Knowledge and the creative economy became the new trend. Since the crisis, resources were allocated to support "innovation-centric entrepreneurship", and most of this support comes in the form of policies. (Klingler and Pardo, 2019). New companies have also started occupying major shares in the market; for example, Naver, Kakao, and Celltrion are dominant in their own fields. As knowledge-based industries gain more prominence and with the rise of the internet, SMEs are able to compete in the global field too. There has also been a rise in self-employed people in the service industries (Jung, 2022). But amidst a fierce global competition, the government leadership is not enough; the private sector must take the lead. This paper explores the state's role in fostering service sectors and the startup scene in Korea, and Park Geun-hye's creative economy policy, which established the Centre for Creative Economy and Innovation to lead the change. The paper argues that Korea's transition to a post-industrial

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¹ South Korea will be referred to as Korea from here on.

economy has not reduced the role of the state; rather, it has transformed it, now the state acts as a facilitator of innovation ecosystems, collaborations with startups, corporations and academia. The Creative Economy and Innovation (CCEI) illustrates how the state actively facilitates the construction of environments that enable entrepreneurial activities and technological advancements. By looking at the interaction of startups, conglomerates and academia and the restructuring of industrial priorities the paper demonstrates that the state still plays a crucial role in the economic development and transformation.

2. Research Methodology

The proposed study uses a qualitative approach to examine the evolving role of state in economic development. It has primarily used secondary sources and used the case study of creative economy and innovation initiative to look at the role of the state at facilitating innovation.

3. Shift To Post-Industrial State

With economic development the economy gradually begins to shift from manufacturing to services, thus from industrial to post-industrial. Daniel Bell (1976) writes that the “codification of theoretical knowledge and the new relation of science to technology” is the central feature of post-industrial society. He mentions how the post-industrial society sees “the growing importance of research and development for invention and innovation” (Bell, 1976). Theoretical knowledge is the axis around which the economic growth and the stratification of the society will be based. Focus on innovation will be the benchmark and the state will be focusing on achieving this. There will be a shift from “mechanical technology to intellectual technology” which will use new softwares, algorithms for running the new high technology. This will lead to the growth of start-ups which will use their educational and technical skills for the development of new services and new software technologies. Knowledge will thus become the most valuable resource.

For the research and development of new innovations the strong educational and technical foundations cannot be compromised. Thus, there is also the growth of higher education with particular focus on science and technology. Education is increasingly being seen as the tool to gain social mobility (Bell, 1976). But this doesn't mean that the focus is exclusively on developing a techno-scientific state. There is also the growth of personnel services as the disposable income rises and thus, we see the growth of alternate spaces, new forms of entertainment services and aesthetics, experimental services. Entrepreneurs are crucial in stimulating the process of innovation and productivity in the economy, enabling job creation, competitiveness according to the Schumpeterian vision. The Schumpeterian theory was based on

the claim that entrepreneurial activity will launch new opportunities for growth in the economy, and innovative initiatives will nurture economic life (Ferreira et al. 2016).

Bell (1976) mentions how the post-industrialized society focuses more on initiating/innovating the products rather than making the products. The production of the goods will be multinational with the headquarters focusing on the concept, innovation, design and marketing.

The shift to service based economy reflects the trend of most advanced economies where after rapid industrialization, a shift takes towards the service sector. The US is a typical example of it, where the service sector is the dominant one. The major economies in the world are following the trend of shifting focus from large industries to nurturing “entrepreneurship and start-up developmental policies” (Lee and Kim, 2019).

The post-industrial society has culminated in the emergence of creative society, where there are various transitions taking place like new occupational structures, new cultural values, integration of local markets into the global (Anderson. 2023). Whilst in the twentieth century inventions were not connected with markets but by the end of twentieth century, industrial R&D have become a crucial part of the market, inventions connected with market consideration.

4. South Korea Gradually Shifting Towards the Service Sector- Focus on Start-Ups And SMEs

The 1997 financial crisis pushed Korea to shed its image as a “catch-up” industrial state to a new dimension of “creative” economy, where the focus was on increasing R&D to “improve knowledge flows and technology transfer across the innovation system” (OECD Report, 2021). Post crisis, the government continued to select and guide new industries most significantly the information technology, knowledge economy, cultural industry. Industrial policies “survived and evolved” and it is now more “reactive” to the changes in the economy and fine tuning based on it, rather than being “proactive and developmental” (Hundt. David Ross, 2014). This reflects in the government’s drive to promote innovation and service sectors, where they are taking inspiration from the trajectory of most advanced economies, rather than identifying and nurturing new industries who could replace the earlier giants. The government’s role as a facilitator is still present, it helps “Korean firms access overseas markets through Free Trade Agreements” (Hundt. David Ross, 2014). Government organisations like KOTRA continue to play an important role in accessing overseas markets, by providing strategies.

The government is now carefully crafting state policies to foster a new generation of economic leaders, particularly focusing on services, startups and SMEs. The startups are claimed to increase the “dynamics of the market ” contribute to the economy’s growth by “creating and forming new market” (Choi, Han, and Kwak, 2021). But at the same time the government is well aware about the elephant in the room, i.e the chaebols. The chaebols have acquired

tremendous power in the economy and no growth model can probably ignore it and thus the government has crafted its policies by roping in the chaebols too. This got to life in Park Geun Hye's Creative Economy policy. The area where the state has shed off its old developmental state image is in the financial sector. The state completely withdrew from the capital market and gave independence to the financial sector, the Bank of Korea independence and many new private banks came up. Also allowed foreign entities access to the capital market of Korea.

The number of SMEs in South Korea has increased exponentially, and it provides the highest employment, but its share in the GDP as compared to the large firms like Chaebols remains small. The wage and productivity levels are also disparate, exacerbating inequalities and fueling the demands for more “economic democratisation” (Connell, 2014). The share of the service sector (56.8) towards the economy is still not as much as compared to the OECD members (which stands at 70.1). South Korea is still one of the “most export-dependent industrialised nations” (US International Trade Administration, 2023). The potential of SMEs are not realised as they are mostly stuck as suppliers and subcontractors to the big firms, limited access to “financial and human resources”, leading to the limitation in developing innovative abilities (Connell, 2014). The R&D is mostly limited to the large private firms, whereas the SMEs do not invest much in R&D. The productivity of SME is also lower than the large ones and very few actually grow into larger ones. There are also cases where IT services with good potential are “purchased by large corporations from captive supplier companies in their groups” (Choi et al, 2013). Thus, there is a growing need for the government to foster the growth of high-quality services.

Korea has also targeted “high value-added global services” like education, content creation, software development, and tourism. Amongst start-ups it is claimed that innovative start-ups have higher chances of attaining high growth and thus the state focuses more on ‘innovation-driven entrepreneurship’ for national economic growth (Choi, Han and Kwak, 2021). These innovative start-ups are expected to be the new drivers of economic growth. The South Korean government has moved on from focusing simply on fostering the SMEs to “stimulating innovative or technology-driven entrepreneurship” (Choi, Han and Kwak, 2021). In order for firms to gain competitive advantage in the already oversaturated markets today it is essential that they invest in R&D for innovation, which can improve their core competence and secure “competitive advantage” (Choi, Han and Kwak, 2021).

The advantage of South Korea lies in the fact that it already has high quality human capital to support the growth of innovative start-ups. One of the major requirements for technology-driven start-ups is the need for highly skilled, knowledgeable, R&D affinity which already exists in Korea due to its well-developed educational sector.

(Klinger and Pardo, 2019) mark out three distinct phases of innovation. 1961-1990: Chaebol led innovation where the chaebols were the major source of high-quality employers

with the aim of “catch-up” industrialization and chaebols as the “drivers of innovative activity”. From 1997 a new churning can be seen as taking place where entrepreneurs are also taking charge of innovation. Klingler and Pardo (2019) identify the phase from 1997-2001 as the “separate chaebol entrepreneur innovation”. Start-ups and chaebols became visible forces shaping the industrial policy, offering high quality employment and both involved in R&D for innovation separately. From 2003 the phase of “embedded chaebol-entrepreneurial innovation starts”. The state realised after the dotcom crash that there was a need to link start-ups with existing economic structure, in Korea it would be the chaebols. It became evident that for the start-up to be successful they need to be “embedded in chaebol production and sales channel”

Government policies are essential to help startups due to their high risk investments and to help them survive against monopolies with huge resources and these policies might help create the ecosystem to sustain the start-ups (Choi, Han and Kwak, 2021). In South Korea this was clearly evident in Creative economy strategy.

5. The Role of State

In the developmental state the industrial policies and public financial institutions were instrumental in shaping the economy. The state was careful enough to restrict entry of foreign firms which could potentially harm the growth of domestic firms. Traditionally the Korean state has been heavily involved in the industrialization and the development of its economy. Whilst the involvement of the state in the economy has decreased with the growth of Chaebols and the financial crisis, the state has not completely taken a back seat and rather it has shifted the focus of industrial policies towards fostering creativity and entrepreneurship amongst the fledgling firms (Klingler-Vidra Robyn, Pardo Ramon. 2019).

The Korean state has played an important role “in developing Korea’s Science and Technology capability” (Bak, 2014). The developmental state also tried to promote SMEs, which picked up pace in the 1990s. It tried to export SMEs, but most of these exported SMEs were subcontractors which helped in the “expansion of chaebols”, through the strategy of “vertical integration and sustained subcontractor relations” (Debanes, 2014). The government policies for fostering an entrepreneurial ecosystem consist of “entrepreneurial education, business incubation, technological development, policy funding, overseas entry and legal systems” (Choi, Han and Kwak, 2021).

The KODIT and KOTECH were instrumental in alleviating the “credit constraints” of especially the tech based SMEs. During the period of 1997, dot com bubble crash and 2008 economic crisis these agencies were “actively mobilised” by the state. (Debanes, 2014).

While the role of state post financial crisis has evolved, new instruments were also developed to guide the economy. There is a rise of “public-private partnerships” (especially the

government working with the chaebols), “geographic locations” (like economic zones, now there are innovation districts, smart cities, tech parks). There are also changes in the regulatory policies used by the state, like moving away from price control, FDI restrictions to “selection of technological standards and management of international treaties” (Debanes. 2014). Signing of FTAs with countries with the help of KOTRA has helped expand the market.

The Korean government's most significant role which continues to leave a deep mark in the society is the role of “an institution builder.” State funded research institutes were set to meet “the technological needs of local industries in the transition to heavy from light industry” (Bak, 2014). The main goal was to penetrate different markets and thus most of the R&D was based keeping in mind the aspect of marketability, this makes the case of Korean science and technology distinctive (Bak, 2014). Through the industrial and public policies the state seeks to place itself in a relevant position “in the dynamics of generation and diffusion of knowledge” (Gordon, 2019).

Post 2008 global crisis stuck in the middle of rising China (cannot match on price) and advanced Japan (cannot match on quality), South Korea has tried to make use of both “value for money” in order to survive its exporter status (Roach and Lam, 2010). To incentivize more R&D for innovation, the government has also announced the “expansion of tax deductions for business investments”, this is to make use of its comparative advantage in technology and design (Roach and Lam, 2010). To sustain its economic growth it is suggested that the government policy must focus on “three fundamentals- R&D investments, service sector reforms and regional development” (Roach and Lam, 2010). Korea’s strong “developmental mindset” alongwith with the partnership of chaebols to “drive innovation, economic growth and job creation” has shaped much of the entrepreneurial promotion in the state since the financial crisis (Klingler and Pardo 2019).

Can industrial policies work to stimulate and foster entrepreneurship? Most of the industrial policies tend to focus on large scale industries, avoid industrial concentration, correct or prevent market failures and thus most often startups slip away from the focus of these industrial policies. But the dominance of traditional manufacturing has weakened and instead a knowledge based economy is emerging where new entrepreneurial businesses are gaining more prominence. It is argued that only under suitable institutions can entrepreneurial activities witness true success and as such government policies moulding these institutional structures are essential (Minniti, 2008). There are many kinds of policies that the government may engage with like attracting venture capital, providing subsidies for R&D and low interest rate loans, tax benefits, creation of formal and informal support systems like training programs, research parks, helping connect with universities, research institutions and other private actors to foster an entrepreneurial ecosystem (Minniti, 2008). Governments are helping high-tech startups, fostering R&D ecosystem to make these entrepreneurs more competitive.

The start-up policy intends to “spur job creation”, “foster more balanced growth away from the chaebol”, “support chaebol innovation²” (Klingler and Pardo 2019). The innovation centres with “chaebols as key partners” were designed to benefit “start-up products and talent” (Klingler and Pardo 2019).

6. Park Geun Hye- Creative Economy, Centre For Creative Economy And Innovation

The Korean startups do not have longevity due to direct competition with the chaebols, as compared to China, US where they tend to integrate rising start-ups through M&A (Schawk and Frassinetti, 2021). There is a greater need and opportunities for Korean SMEs to collaborate with large companies, “to enhance innovation diffusion” (Pak, 2010).

When the Park Geun government came to power they stressed “job-centred creative economy” as the vehicle for growth. She stated in her opening speech that as the economic paradigm in world witnesses rapid shifts, her government would work on fostering the creative economy, “The convergence of science and technology with industry, the fusion of culture with industry and the blossoming of creativity made possible by the breaking down of barriers between industries together define a creative economy” (Park Geun Hye, Inaugural Address 2013). She earmarked science, technology and IT industry as her main economic priority. Park Geun-hye had laid down several strategies for the creative economy like fostering the growth of start-up nations, software the main driver of future businesses, creation of new markets and jobs, construction of a creative economy ecosystem, and promoting SMEs.

Whilst the policy of creative economy was present in Korea since the 90s, its focus was mainly creative industry like culture, art and the local government were the central actors (Cha, Doo-won, 2015). Regional Innovation Systems, composed of three innovation actor groups: universities, industrial enterprises and public research institutes were present in Korea, but they were limited in scope as well as they were concentrated only in particular regions (Chung, 2002). The focus in the introductory period was primarily on the cultural policies, but as Korea’s economy advanced, debates surrounding the need to expand the concept of creative economy also started. The debates focused on the need to create a “synergy among the IT, traditional manufacturing and cultural industries” (Cha, Doo-won, 2015).

The Park Geun Hye administration was quite aware of the fact that to foster innovation and develop new technologies, business models and services it is essential that there is a suitable ecosystem to cultivate them (Connell, 2014). This innovation ecosystem consists of many dynamic actors like the state, organisations/firms, research labs, universities, legal, financial and

² Ability of start-ups to “develop technologies faster than conglomerates due to a less hierarchical structure” (Klingler-Vidra Robyn, Pardo Ramon. 2019)

other range of professionals all contribute towards the process of innovation and fostering this ecosystem (Connell, 2014). The state here assumes an important role in facilitating and framing the conditions to ensure a collaborative and productive ecosystem. The state's critical role here is that of a facilitator and coordinator. Formulating policies and strategies to ensure that there is a smooth collaboration amongst the various actors to foster innovation is the role of the state. Creative economy's value lies in its novel imaginative and innovative ideas, and the success lies in its novel qualities.

The Park government had kept innovation at the core of its agenda for creative economy and as such has established a new "Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning" for a smooth collaboration, development, coordination and implementation of policies (Connell, 2014). She also set up the Centre for Creative Economy & Innovative (CCEI), which is a non-profit institution with the aim of supporting SMEs and startups (Jung, Eun and Lee, 2017). The agenda for the Creative Economy was primarily administered by the Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning, which was exclusively established by President Park Geun Hye by absorbing part of the Ministry of Knowledge Economy and part of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (Debanes, 2014). This Ministry was responsible for implementing most of the ICT policies, setting up CCEIs, and funded private incubators. The innovation centres set up across the country with specialised areas and its focus is to nurture the SMEs and startups. These innovation centres were one of the most "visible manifestations of the government creative economy agenda" (Mundy, 2015). It was expected that matching startups with these conglomerates would create a positive synergy, help overcome financial constraints, provide ideas to help innovate, explore new markets and overseas market expansion. CCEI aimed to foster a mentoring platform, "a hub for vocational education", "encourage managerial and technological innovation", "create new markets and jobs" (Jung, Eun and Lee, 2017). The primary aim of the Park Geun Hye government was to create a productive entrepreneurial ecosystem with the various stakeholders, which is expected to provide more job opportunities in the future. These centres were expected to boost the startups and end the dominant reliance on the chaebols for economic growth (Mundy, 2015). This innovation-led growth sought to incorporate the best of the public and private sector to invigorate the process of generating new knowledge, innovation. CCEIs act as regional innovation hubs, they provide support to new businesses in the form of providing R&D services, financing, legal and patent consulting. They also help in the transfer of technology, help develop business models for startups, secure sales channels and access to overseas markets. For regional development the CCEIs foster industries tailored to regional traits, collaborate with regional universities, agencies and the CCEIs also help in job creation, by linking youth from the regions to these startups without the need to go in search of jobs in Seoul or other main cities (UNCTAD, 2017). Recently in the U.S too, there has been the emergence of a new urban model, "where leading edge anchor institutions and companies cluster and connect with start-ups, business incubators and accelerators", these spaces are referred to as the "innovation districts" (Katz and Wagner, 2014).

CCEI's were also envisaged to reduce uneven regional development by enhancing regional and industrial competitiveness. The linking of different chaebols with different regions was expected to distribute resources across the country. These ecosystems are expected to induce and stimulate new collaborations as well as job opportunities. Developing job opportunities in different regions will help reduce the burden on Seoul and revitalise the provinces

Park Geun-hye's Creative Economy Innovation Centers (CCEI) can be compared to U.S. initiatives such as those launched by the Obama administration. The U.S. developed a strong public-private partnership model, involving firms, universities, and government agencies (Atkinson, 2020). This collaboration culture has fostered significant advancements in knowledge and practical applications, driven by a competitive environment among universities aiming to innovate and collaborate with industries. The commercialization of research in the U.S. has led to increased collaboration among stakeholders to achieve common innovation goals. The Obama administration launched various initiatives to boost innovation and competitiveness, including expanding R&D tax credits, patent reform, promoting STEM education, and increasing funding for science agencies. The U.S. also supports mission-oriented research in fields like defence and health and funds universities to conduct basic research. Additionally, government research laboratories, funded by agencies like the Department of Defense and the Department of Health, play a crucial role in achieving research objectives (Atkinson, 2020).

6.1 Link with Chaebols

Park Geun Hye aims to nurture the growth of a new generation of businesses with the help of the already well established big conglomerates. The CCEIs established by the Park government focused on embedding start-ups with the chaebols whilst promoting specific clusters. The CCEIs focused on linking start-ups with chaebols based on specific verticals like Seoul innovation centre which focuses on culture and lifestyle is linked with CJ which focuses on entertainment. Ulsan centre where start-ups focus on ship-building and marine plant, medical automation industry is linked with Hyundai Heavy industries. Since these start-ups are embedded with the chaebols they are also "injecting chaebols with renewed innovation capacity" (Klingler and Pardo 2019). The CCEIs reflect the intention of the state to harness a balanced growth and at the same time promote innovation. Using the resources of chaebols was considered as an effective way to develop a rich entrepreneurial ecosystem. CCEI helps ease the burden of risks taken by entrepreneurs, due to risk sharing with big conglomerates.

Whilst the chaebols act as "anchor partner", the central government pays "half of the operating costs of the CCEIs" and also contributes a portion of the funding for "start-up investment funds" (Klingler and Pardo 2019). These conglomerates along with the local government are linked up with startups and SMEs to support in different speciality areas. For example:- Gwangju region's theme is motor vehicle related startups and Hyundai motors is in

charge, similarly Samsung is involved in the Gyeongbuk region whose theme is “smart factory innovation, convergence type culture and agriculture”. Gyeonggi Province is linked with KT whose key area is related to game industry fintech.

6.2 Link With Universities

The startups are also linked with universities and research institutes to coordinate and exchange research, ideas, technologies. CCEI aimed to foster a mentoring platform, “a hub for vocational education”, “encourage managerial and technological innovation”, “ create new markets and jobs”, (Jung, Eun and Lee 2017).

South Korea is one of the few countries in the world who spends a significant share (more than 4 percent) of their GDP towards R&D and has continually stressed on “upgrading technology and maximising management efficiency” (Jung, 2022). Even the corporations spend a significant portion on R&D, which has made contributions to them becoming a global player in electronics, semiconductors, automobiles etc.

Dong-Won Sohn and Martin Kenney (2007), mentioned that typically Korea had a neat division of roles between Research Institutes and Universities, where Research Institutes had mission-oriented research responsibilities for the government and industries, whereas universities were focused on education. But today due to various incentives for collaboration followed by technological licensing, patenting new technologies has made it attractive for universities to collaborate with industries (Sohn and Kenney 2007).

The Ministry of Education, Ministry of SMEs and Startups, Ministry of Land, Infrastructure and Transport has collaborated to establish ‘Campus Innovation Parks’, whose purpose is to foster a ‘university-centred regional innovation ecosystem’. The motive is to create an ecosystem of high-tech industrial complex and innovation, within university campuses. Universities will act as a bridge to foster local talent and entrepreneurial education, within the local environment. These campus innovation parks are an excellent way to achieve regional development. Universities from different regions can work with industries to foster innovation as well as help in job creation.

In the triple helix model the state, corporate and universities move towards the common direction to “drive a knowledge-based economy as a system of innovation” whose goal is innovation based growth (Cho, 2014). Cooperating with each other helps in the easier integration and commercialisation of knowledge, where universities get access to funds for research and corporates can “capture research discoveries”, fostering a symbiotic relationship (Cho, 2014). Universities, technical institutes, and research institutes have become the hotbeds for new research and development. Many students are spurring new innovations and ideas (Jung, 2022). Public research institutes, which are funded by the government, are also important in inducing

R&D. The government, by inducing the collaboration between industry, drove the innovation growth (Bothwell, 2019).

With rapid changes undergoing in the market, it is essential that Korea maintains its competitive advantage and as such, living labs are becoming a crucial part of the innovation system. In the living labs various stakeholders collaborate and cooperate. The local communities play an important role and it is user-oriented. Cooperation between universities and industries can be crucial in achieving major innovation breakthroughs. They can engage in joint R&D, provide specialised training to the employees as well as also provide consulting services to the enterprises. Input from outsiders can help improve the final product. While fostering a knowledge economy, the government, industry and universities come together to advance new knowledge, talent and innovation. Interactions between them have led to the development of intermediary institutions like science parks, innovation parks (Shvetsova and Lee, 2021).

7. Conclusion

South Korea's journey from a developmental state to a post-industrial society illustrates a remarkable economic transformation driven by strategic state interventions and innovative policies. The transition towards a post-industrial society has been characterised by the rise of the service sector and the proliferation of innovative startups. Policies such as the establishment of the Centres for Creative Economy and Innovation (CCEI) have played pivotal roles in nurturing a knowledge-based economy. These initiatives have aimed to create a supportive ecosystem for high-value services and technological innovation, leveraging the nation's highly educated workforce and advanced technological infrastructure.

Despite significant progress, challenges persist. The dominance of chaebols and disparities between large conglomerates and SMEs pose ongoing hurdles. Addressing these issues requires a balanced approach, ensuring that the benefits of economic growth are widely distributed while fostering a competitive environment that encourages innovation and entrepreneurship.

Looking ahead, South Korea's ability to sustain its post-industrial transformation will depend on continuous adaptation to global economic shifts and technological advancements. The government's role as a facilitator, rather than a direct participant, will be crucial in promoting a dynamic and resilient economy. Emphasising education, research and development, and international collaboration will be key to maintaining Korea's competitive edge. By continuing to support innovation and entrepreneurship while addressing structural challenges, South Korea can solidify its position as a leading post-industrial economy.

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